

ISic0612

I.Sicily inscription 0612

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone marl (local)

Object

exedra

Editor

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Autopsy

2011-06-15

Last Change

2019-07-23 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based on study and autopsy for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 9 September 1970, found against the late wall which links internal columns 3 and 4 in front of room 4 of the west portico of the agora.

Coordinates

37.997990, 14.262601

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20219

Physical Description

A block of 'marna argillosa locale', height 0.66m, width 0.52 m, depth 0.255m. The block is damaged on the left side and upper right, and both the lower left and lower right corners are lost. Traces of a metal staple are preserved in the upper surface, and a single letter lambda is preserved on the right side (presumably relating to the construction of the monument of which the block was a part). The block is probably from the central part of one of the exedra (exedra C) originally situated along the front of the west portico (Burgio 2012: 164).

Dimensions

Height 66 cm

Width 52 cm

Depth 25.5 cm

Layout

Nine lines of Greek text are preserved, almost complete, unevenly centred on the stone.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are neatly and regularly cut, and of standard Hellenistic form, without serifs. Epsilon is notable for having a detached middle bar; beta is not closed.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Line 2-9: 25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. θεοῖς πᾶσι
2. [ο]ἰ στρατευσάμενοι
3. κατὰ ναῦν
4. Ἄλαισῖνοι
5. Καλακτῖνοι
6. Ἑρβιταῖοι
7. Ἀμηστρατῖνοι
8. []Κανίνιον Νίγρον
9. εὐνοίας, ,ξνεκε[ν]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

previous edd: εὐνοία[ς ἔ]νεκε[ν]

Translation (en)

The Halaesini, Kalaktini, Herbitaioi and Amestratini who served on board ship (dedicate) to all the gods (a statue of) [-?] Kaninius Niger, on account of his good will.

Commentary

The missing letters in lines 2 and 9 can be restored without hesitation.

Previous editors have marked the middle letters of line 9 as lost, but clear and sufficient traces of both are visible on the stone. Assuming from the name that Caninius Niger was a Roman citizen, it is likely that his abbreviated praenomen is missing in the gap at the start of line 8, but no trace of a letter is visible. The lack of a patronymic in the naming formula is unusual; there does not however appear to be any space on the stone for its inclusion.

Several members of the Caninius gens are known in Roman Sicily, but none with the cognomen Niger and the individual cannot be identified (Facella 2006: 222). Since the stone records naval service on board one or more ships by members of several local poleis, apparently under the command of a Roman citizen, historians have frequently tried to connect the inscription to a specific naval action, such as the campaigns against pirates in the late 70s and early 60s BC, or the period of the civil wars in the 40s and 30s BC (e.g. Scibona 1971: 5-11). Prestianni Giallombardo (2012: 174-176) has argued that the language of the text suggests generic military service rather than a particular naval event, and the inscription finds obvious parallels in the honours set up by the soldiers who served in the garrison at Eryx (ISic1177 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1177>]) and in a text set up by infantry soldiers at Solunto (ISic1130 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1130>]). Sicilians served in Roman fleets both in major wars abroad and in naval garrison duties around

Sicily throughout the Republican period (Pinzone, A. 2004. I socii navales siciliani. In M. Caccamo Caltabiano, L. Campagna and A. Pinzone (eds), Nuove prospettive della ricerca sulla Sicilia del III sec. a.C. Archeologia, Numismatica, Storia. Messina: Di.Sc.A.M.: 11-34; Prag, J. R. W. 2007. Auxilia and gymnasia: a Sicilian model of Roman Republican Imperialism. *Journal of Roman Studies* 97: 68-100 [<https://doi.org/10.3815/000000007784016061>] ; cf. Facella 2006: 220-221 and Pinzone 2011). The presence of the four communities named here, all from this region of Sicily, finds a parallel in a similar, still unpublished, text also from Halaesa set up by cavalrymen from Halaesa and other communities; it is also tempting to link the inscription to the evidence of bronze coinage from the region, usually dated to the Timoleontic period, which attests to a regional alliance, but no direct connection is possible (Scibona, G. 2009a. Decreto sacerdotale per il conferimento della euerghesia a Nemenios in Halaesa. In G. Scibona and G. Tigano (eds), *Alaisa-Halaesa. Scavi e ricerche (1970-2007)*. Messina: Regione Siciliana. 97-112, at 107-110).

The inscription cannot be precisely dated, but the style of the inscription and the letters suggest a date in the second or first century BC.

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